

SPIRITUALITY - HUMAN SPIRITUALITY AT THE STAGE OF HISTORICAL DEVELOPMENT

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When it is said that man is the flower of nature, of all being, it is implied that he has this trait, that is, the possibility of being the owner of high spirituality. We will not see this possibility in other creatures. While material objects give a person physical food and energy, spirituality gives him spiritual food and strength. Content only with material maintenance – inherent in unconscious and soulless creatures. And the pursuit of spirituality is a virtue inherent only to the human being, the owner of spirit and mind. Spirituality is such a complex social phenomenon as the set of the mental and spiritual world of a person.

Only those with high spirituality and enlightenment will live as glue, my country, and it will be happiness for them to show kindness to others, to support those who need help, and to guide them the right way. Those who have high spirituality and compassion have hard work on their heads, make it easy for a person who has fallen into grief, become a partner in his grief, become an ointment for pain, make out a hojati, take care of orphans. In those who are the owner of such a quality, national pride, a sense of national pride, orientality will be strong. They consider it a glory for themselves to defend the honor of their nation, the benefit of el-ulusi, to show their wealth, Soul, Sacrifice and examples of heroism in the path of protection of the motherland if a security is born to independence. It is also not very correct to conclude from the above that only enlightened people would have a high spirituality. Looking at the history of mankind, not all people with spirituality have always been enlightened. At the same time we can see that not all people with knowledge, enlightenment were highly spiritual. For such people, our people rightfully used the proverbial phrase "become a scientist, but not a person", which expressed deep meaning in itself. In other words, there are people who are not scientists. Without a scientist, but with a high morale. There are scientists who do not deserve a human breed. This one weighs. There is no benefit from them to the land. As our people find and say, Rice will not be without kurmak. This phrase has been used only in proportion to certain people of science whose spirituality is rare in life. Such people were viewed with contempt. On the contrary, those who took the example of the people of Science, who harmoniously embodied spirituality and

enlightenment, dreamed that their children would become such people. Along with the above phrase, our people also used the phrase "Be not a scientist." This situation does not mean that spirituality and enlightenment deny each other. On the contrary, spirituality and enlightenment are mutual, closely related factors that persecute each other, promote the maturation of Man and society. As our president said, We can see which period of our history we do not take, the pursuit of ilmu enlightenment and high spirituality in our country has never stopped, which has become evident even in the most difficult and complex times as an immortal embodiment of the genius of our people. Our ancestors from time immemorial considered the invaluable wealth of knowledge, education and upbringing as the most basic condition and guarantee of human perfection and prosperity of the nation.

In conclusion, it can be said that any country has its own spirituality that elevates this spirituality. So in our country, too, it is necessary to educate children in the spirit of spirituality from a preschool institution of course it is also a mistake to limit yourself to this, because this spirituality of ours goes back several years, which means that it is also advisable to draw attention to families. In order for us to strengthen the Enlightenment, it is necessary to obtain more knowledge, people who read books are definitely enlightened.

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